

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ANALYSIS OF A WORK OF ART AND WAYS OF ORGANIZING ITS TEACHING

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Abstract

Literature is a form of manifestation of all emotions from the heart. We can experience these emotions while reading literary works with their depth. The works of art reflect all the happenings in society. The lives lived by human beings are presented in their imagination and reality. If we pay attention to the themes of the works, all the feelings and events necessary for a person to live in life have been found. Reading works of art and understanding its content will be one of the most pressing problems today and forever. Because works of art are a kind of mirror of human life. Lives, dreams, images and their characters, the bad or good events they experienced are facts that teach us. Each of the works of art is a life lesson. It is like a ray of sunshine on the life path of the students. He shines his light into the dark world. Our students are our tomorrow, our hope. Each one of them is a bud, and those buds grow in our hands, they step into life. Their primary upbringing is in the hands of their parents and teachers. Literature and its treasure helps us at this time. Artistic works have a special feature in literature. The works are a source for studying the history of our literature, our traditions, human character, and the history of literary development. Literature plays an important role in understanding life, enriching oneself, maintaining relationships with people for self-education, and forming a strong person in life. Literary works are a free tool for people. From the time people are born, they study artistic works until the end of their lives. The basis of this foundation for every person is laid in secondary schools. The teacher should make the students love the works of art so that they read them all the time. While studying the works, they should be able to look at the content accurately and distinguish the positive and negative sides.

Keywords: artistic work, methodology, student.

Introduction

Since the process of teaching literary works is considered important, certain works have been done for their teaching in secondary schools. Literary works form the main part of literature lessons in secondary schools. Each of these works is included in the textbook based on the requirements. Each of our students means the destiny of our future and state. The work to be done by the teacher is very responsible. We must raise a mother, a soldier, a father, a family head, and most importantly, a good person and a citizen who loves his country. In this way, artistic works come to us. The artistic works given in our textbooks open up various opportunities for us on this path. We prepare them for life by teaching the content of the works and the problems the writer opens. In addition, the study of artistic works improves students' oral and written speech. Students' vocabulary increases, speech becomes beautiful. In his speeches, he understands the intricacies of the meaning of words and thoughts, and develops the ability to express them. Even talented students are encouraged to write their own stories and poems. Artifacts are people's best friends. Writers always think of their readers and become a light in their lives.

According to the age level of each class, the subject of artistic works is taught to them. In each of the works, they learn educational points for themselves and apply them in life. At this time, mastering the content of the works is very important. Students should read the works superficially, not go through and grasp its content. The purpose of the artist must be fulfilled. Every artist writes his feelings, dreams, dreams and

reality, the world he wants to see. Learn about his feelings, feel the content of the writer and it is up to the teachers to convey it as they did. Therefore, the teacher must teach each of the works of art according to the content standards.

Thus, an adequate understanding of the content of artistic works solves three issues at the same time. First, the child's worldview expands and deepens, his knowledge and emotions are enriched. Secondly, the educational effect is strengthened. Thirdly, it helps the enrichment and development of students' language.

About the essence of the concept of "analysis of a work of art".

Acquaintance with artistic examples that are relevant not only for the period in which they were written, but also for today and the future, initially begins at school. As far as we know, the teaching of artistic works in the modern lesson takes place in three stages. The last stage is devoted to the organization of the work to be done on the analysis of artistic samples. Analyzing lessons is a very important, but also a complex process. Proper organization of this process requires keeping a number of important conditions in the center of attention. These issues can be grouped as follows:

1. "The content of the concept of analysis.
2. Principles of analysis of the work.
3. The aspects covered by the analysis, the structure of the analysis.
4. Ways of analyzing the work". [21, 26].

First of all, let's take a look at the concept of "analysis". The analysis is explained in this way: "Analysis is a logical principle, a research method,

through which the studied subject is divided into its constituent parts and then each of them is studied separately: this is done because elements separated during the analysis should be combined into a whole enriched with new knowledge with the help of another logical principle - synthesis" [25, 49]. In order to organize the analysis of a work of art at the appropriate level, purposeful work on the text should be done. This work requires a creative ability from a literature teacher, along with a deep knowledge of literary studies.

The attitude to the analysis of the artistic work has led to the emergence of different approaches from time to time. A group of research scholars have opined that analysis lessons are a very difficult process for students. They clarified their opinion that the task of the school is not to educate a literary critic, but a personality. In our opinion, this issue is somewhat difficult to agree with. Because artistic works are created as a result of the attitude of writers and poets to the surrounding world. In addition to the clearly expressed ideas in these examples, there are points that are not understood by the students in the reading process. It is necessary to organize analysis classes to overcome such difficulties. It may then be asked whether How should analysis lessons dedicated to the teaching of artistic works be structured? What important issues should be focused on? First of all, let's note that the term school analysis is used in lessons dedicated to the analysis of artistic examples. "School analysis differs from other types of analysis of the work, such as philosophical analysis, psychological analysis, aesthetic analysis, literary analysis, etc., according to a number of features". However, explaining the relationship between these two types of analysis by their identity can seriously harm the progress of the work. Sometimes, literature teachers try to teach students a lot of information about the science of literary studies during the analysis of a literary work. they require this knowledge in the next lessons. Today, analysis lessons should be based not on the rich knowledge of the teacher, but on his creative skills. Of course, we are also in favor of the teacher's mastery of his specialty. However, the main goal of modern education is not to acquire a large amount of knowledge, but to teach the necessary knowledge and turn this knowledge into skills. Students must acquire knowledge themselves as a result of research. It is this work system that forms the basis of analysis lessons. Using the possibilities of literary analysis should not overshadow the specificity of school analysis.

Method

The main purpose of the analysis of artistic works in literature classes is to enable students to develop as personalities and acquire the necessary skills. By the way, let us also note that inculcating the national and spiritual values expressed in artistic works to students has a significant impact on their personality formation. Commenting on the issue, Methodist S. Huseinoglu writes: "It is clear from what has been said that it is not correct to draw a border between literary studies and school analysis, or to consider one of them completely

dependent on the others. The relationship between them is not only in the form of subordination, but also in the form of cooperation." [12, 72]. The following principles should be taken into account when analyzing works of art at school: or it is not correct to consider one of them completely dependent on the others. The relationship between them is not only in the form of subordination, but also in the form of cooperation." [22, 72]. The following principles should be taken into account when analyzing works of art at school: or it is not correct to consider one of them completely dependent on the others. The relationship between them is not only in the form of subordination, but also in the form of cooperation." [19, 82]. The following principles should be taken into account when analyzing works of art at school:

1. "The principle of ideality.
2. The principle of historicity.
3. The principle of interaction and conditioning of the content and form of the artistic work.
4. Pedagogical principle.
5. The principle of reconciliation of analysis ways and methods". [15, 184]

Determining the idea of the work during the analysis of artistic works constitutes the essence of the principle of ideality. The overlap between the author's intention and the reader's position is one of the main indicators of the accurate perception of the artistic example by the students. During the analysis, the historical conditions in which the work was written should be taken into account, and it should be analyzed in relation to the modern era. It is useful to provide students with additional information about the period in which the literary work was written and the social and political situation.

The principle of historicity its violation during the analysis may harm the author's position, and it may also cause difficulty in students' understanding of the work.

As mentioned in the methodological literature, "the principle of the unity of content and form requires the expectation of equality between what is talked about in the work and how it is expressed". [3, 133]. The content of the work is the main criterion that determines its form. The content of the work of art is the main thing, but it is wrong to consider the form as passive.

Pedagogical principle during the analysis of artistic works, it is necessary to take into account the age and knowledge level of students, the possibilities of understanding the work. For this, it is important for the teacher to have high pedagogical skills. At the same time, it is one of the main issues to keep students' interests and demands in the focus of analysis classes.

It is possible to analyze works of art in different ways. "The way in which the analysis will be conducted is determined by taking into account the volume, genre, complexity, training and educational tasks of the work". [13, 187]. Using different methods in analysis lessons allows for more efficient organization of work. However, which analysis method the teacher will choose depends on the genre and character of the work, as well as on the tasks to be performed during the lesson. In the methodological literature, it is

recommended to use the following methods of analysis in training:

1. **"Analysis after the author (analysis of the work as a whole)**
2. **Analysis of images.**
3. **Problem-topic analysis"**[9, 188].

During the analysis behind the teacher, the events in the work, the idea of the work, the main issues reflected in it are filtered with the help of the teacher, and the students' understanding of the work is ensured. At this time, the understanding of the work as a whole is the main goal underlying the work system. However, understanding the concept of "integrity" as the integrity of the form of the work can seriously damage the progress of the work. Because it is not possible to include in the analysis all the issues found in some large-scale works during the teaching, and there is no need for it. During the school analysis, this type of analysis should be given more priority in grades V-IX. In addition to the analysis of the work as a whole, the involvement of images in the analysis is widely used in school practice.

The writer first expresses himself with his artistic examples and shares his personal thoughts about the society in which he lives with his readers. The works of fiction are created as a result of the attitude observed by the writer in the real society. Therefore, it is the teacher's success to bring every problem reflected in the artistic work, to refine the artistic images, to the analysis. "The writer has the right to see life and people not only as they are, but as they can be, as he wishes, as he wants to see in the work of art. In addition to the question of "what is the truth of life like", the writer answers the question of "how should the truth of life be" [6, 191]. The author tries to convey the truths of life with the help of images. The images he created in the work reflect the characteristics of several people he saw in society. These images play a big role in conveying the main idea of the work to the readers. It is not accidental that the behavior and characters of the heroes in the fictional work attract the students more. With the help of the ideal hero created by the writer, he shows the way to solve the issues that bother him, influences the formation of national and moral values in students. The characters in the work of art have different characters, of course they differ from each other. This is their behavior and h The characters in the work of art have different characters, of course they differ from each other. This is their behavior and h The characters in the work of art have different characters, of course they differ from each other. This is their behavior and h

As mentioned, problematic analysis is also used in the study of artistic works. There are different approaches in the scientific-methodical literature about the essence of the concept of problem analysis. If a group of researchers - methodologists connect this analysis with the teaching of literary knowledge in classes, some interpret the solution reflected in the work by the writer as an investigation of important issues. However, it should not be forgotten that the basis of problem analysis is the active activity of students. Using different types of questions to develop

the ability of students to work independently during the use of this analysis method creates conditions for efficient and effective construction of the work. Thus, the content of these types of questions prepared by the teacher should be structured in such a way that the answers to these questions cannot be found in the literature textbook. At the same time, these questions should be chosen according to the interests and needs of the students, and should encourage them to research. That is why it is not correct to consider every question as a problematic question during the analysis. Such questions create a problem situation during the lesson by requiring different answers from the students. Problem questions differ from other types of questions due to a number of features. From this point of view, these differences can be grouped as follows:

1. These types of questions should be different from other types of questions due to their level of difficulty.
2. When choosing these questions, they should be attractive and should be asked directly related to the problem in the work of art.
3. Problem questions should allow for the opening of several problems.

The use of different analysis methods in school analysis allows for a better understanding of artistic works by students. At the end of the work, the students who clarified the ways of solving the main problem raised in the literary work and the main position of the author during the analysis acquire the necessary knowledge and skills.[8]

The importance of the analysis of works of art

A work of art develops imagination in students. The great physicist Albert Einstein wrote: "I believe in intuition and imagination. Imagination is more important than knowledge, because knowledge is limited, and imagination encompasses everything in the world, imagination catalyzes progress and is the source of evolution. Not only philological scientists, but also great psychological scientists of the world have conducted extensive research on this quality of a work of art." [16,29] According to the information given by AA Alizadeh, the famous French psychologist T. Ribault conducted extensive research on this. That psychologist comes to the same conclusion as Albert Einstein. He writes: "But imagination discovers..."

Artistic works affect a person and the society in which he exists. People are interested in works that they love and that affect their spiritual world. "Fiction is a spiritual bridge between its creators and listeners or readers." Writers say that works of art are a companion to the science of history to study the past. If the science of history studies and characterizes the history of the occurrence of events, then fiction revives the past with artistic expressions and can show the bad and good things and distinguish between them. [17, 52]

When we think about it, we realize that works of art are our lives. Each of us is a hero of a work of art. Everyone has a story and is waiting for its ending. When the student reads each work, he finds his image. Thus, he follows the characters in the work, compares his story to them and learns certain life lessons for himself.

Ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle wrote: "When writers imitate the lives, actions and activities of people, those people are always either good or bad." Human characters are always more inclined towards good and bad. People are always chosen according to their goodness, sins, good and bad deeds. Thus, in the works, we either imitate those who are worse or better than ourselves, or those who are like ourselves." [4, 53]

Works of art embody feelings, thoughts and dreams that affect a person. The plot content of the works creates a new world, a sublime feeling inside the person. A student who reads novels, short stories, and stories can better understand the character of all the characters in the work and compare them with people in life when he feels and individualizes each work. Sometimes he puts himself in the shoes of the characters. In this way, the student gets to know people of all kinds, and their communication skills are formed. The student takes an example from each work. The feelings of hatred and love are awakened in their hearts. Analyzes the images themselves. For example, the sad life of Shirin and Leyli, who are the heroes of our works, is a life lesson for our girls. It is impossible that the love and adventures of Majnun and Farhad gained sympathy in the hearts of the students and they did not get burned by their troubles. [12, 145]

"While reading the works of Nizami Ganjavi, N. Tusi came to the conclusion that the actions, behaviors, and speeches of the characters leave certain traces on the reader. For example, the reader takes examples from Farhad, Khosrov, and Shirin, hates the characters' bad actions and unpleasant actions, and does not want to apply those actions in their own lives. He educates his characters on the example of literary heroes. That is, literature immerses a person in thoughts, increases his sensitivity, calls him to life, strengthens his inner world, and in general, forms the moral qualities that a person needs. [10, 54]

The description of nature and the external appearance of people in the artistic work in detail with the means of artistic expression helps the students to understand the way of life and the inner world of the person in the work. Sometimes, natural phenomena occurring in nature are connected with images. While learning the content, the student imagines the inner world of the characters and remembers their actions. This process later leads to understanding the idea of the work. If we are trying to teach students the aesthetic idea hidden in the bottom layer of the artistic work, then we should draw attention to every detail and every word in the artistic work. Only then will the student try to understand the main idea of the work of art.

The well-known educator Ajdar Agayev advised children to develop reading habits from an early age. He considers it important to start with picture books to create interest in preschool children and to develop thinking and understanding skills by discussing pictures with adults. After this situation becomes a habit in students, they have a desire to read literary works. Ajdar Agayev evaluates the topic of the main work for high school students. Therefore, he advised teachers to choose and read works of art that instill

feelings of family, heroism, love for the country, nature, friendship, faith, etc. [2, 55]

Farahim Sadigov also agrees with Ajdar Agayev. Both of them suggest choosing the most interesting plots when choosing a topic with students.

Sukhomlinsky wrote: "Reading is the window that opens to children to see the world and to know themselves." [8, 56] A number of educators are of the opinion that it is necessary to find time to read fiction, otherwise one's brain will dry up.

Ilyas Efendiyev wrote that perfect works of art affect the reader's thoughts and feelings and improve the reader thoroughly. [3, 57]

The conclusion of these scientists shows that it is important to master the content of the works taught in the classroom down to the smallest details. Because the writer reveals a great truth through an episode that sometimes seems ordinary to us. Also, the perfect understanding of these episodes has a strong impact on the development of the student's imagination.

Our prominent Azerbaijani methodologists have also spoken about the importance of teaching the content of an artistic work, and have given a lot of information about it in their books. Soltan Huseynoglu has a wide opinion about this in his book. He states that: "Students' speech is polished and developed during the comprehension of artistic works. In literary works, students admire the beauty of our language, artistic words and phrases, and the richness of deep subtextual meanings of the work. The artistic language features of the works, the ability of the artists to use words and expressions, artistry, imagery are explained to the students. Thus, the process of shaping and enriching the student's speech is carried out." [17, 158]

Our dear Methodist Soltan Huseynoglu realized the great importance of the artistic works given in the textbooks for the students in the high school, and it is important to teach their main idea-content rather than memorizing the works. He writes about the content of the work of art: "The work of art is a part of life." it is possible to accept it as a condition of his opinion. In the works, life is distinguished by its complexity, diversity and multifacetedness. The works reflect the characters' feelings, thoughts, lives, and the development of the socio-political situation. It is not true to see a work of art as a static, closed source. If we add the reader's "dreams outside the work" to the works, Each of our esteemed writers is of the opinion that no perfect analysis can fully cover the content of a work of art. This is one of the reasons why the artistic work is always discussed and searched for by changing generations." [2, 224]

Fakhraddin Yusifov talked about the importance of works for human life. He says: "Artistic works help in the formation of skills necessary for life in the development of a person as a personality. The development of people who are strong in the face of all difficulties, who find solutions when faced with problems, who are able to hold on to life, gain a healthy and strong position, is one of the important issues for our future. In the future, the role of literary works is great in the formation of a citizen who is worthy of the country, nation, and family and who is able to build his

own life. Therefore, the process of teaching artistic works is important. Of course, it is the teacher's responsibility to carry out this process in the best quality way." [6, 231]

About the importance of teaching the content of works and language features, methodist B

Sing a ghazal to be famous,

Be easy to read and write. Of course, here we are talking not about simplicity, but about artistry, expressing deep thoughts and complex issues in a clear, understandable artistic language." [7, 58]

Each artistic work leads a person to new emotions, dreams and thoughts. While reading the work, we feel the emotions of the characters, as if we are dreaming of the character, experiencing his emotions and desires. After the work is finished, he tries to apply the effects he left on us in our own lives and helps us to make our dreams come true and live life as a strong person. The difference between literature and science is that the artistic works we study touch the hearts of the students and transmit their emotions from person to person. The works read during childhood are always remembered by a person, because the aesthetic and emotional perception of artistic works becomes stronger during childhood, and the spiritual component of a person's personality begins to form. Each work awakens and enriches different emotions in the student. They have love, mercy, compassion, forms feelings such as hatred etc. By presenting the people in the works, people's lives, different worlds, interpersonal relationships and other events to the students as models, we can achieve the formation of the students as a personality, to grow as a self-confident individual towards the environment. Just learning the content of a work of art is an important tool for a person.

Scientific-theoretical bases of the analysis of artistic works

A. Garabagli, who is the author of the textbook for the higher school called "Methodology of Azerbaijani Literature" published in 1968, has extensively discussed the principles of analysis of epic works and ways of analysis of lyrical works in chapter III of the textbook. Talking about the general methods and components of the analysis, the analysis of the copies, their characterization, and the organization of classes dedicated to the analysis of the copies, A. Garabagli writes: "When analyzing the work, it is necessary to characterize the hero, reveal the artistic features of the work, describe the landscape and objects, the structure and ideological direction of the work separately. there is little to analyze. It is necessary to create a connection between them, to put all of them at the service of the general analysis of the work. Therefore, all elements of the analysis should ultimately be united on a single line and help to highlight the main idea of the work. [12, 92]

If we briefly summarize the opinions of A. Garabağli about the activity of the teacher during the analysis of the work, we will get the result that during the analysis of the artistic work, it is necessary to motivate the students to work independently as much as possible. The teacher should try to keep the students away from memorized words and repeated ideas, and not to make them accept their opinion mechanically. It

should enable students to independently find the idea, content, and opinion of the author, and teach them how to justify their ideas by bringing examples and evidence from the work.

J. Ahmadov published in 1991 "Methodology of Literary Teaching" in chapter VII called "Methodology of Literary Works Analysis" for high school, some general issues of the literary work and its analysis, the place of artistic works in the school, the study of artistic works, the ideas and ideas of artistic works it talks about the methodical analysis of artistic features. J. Ahmadov, who also mentions the analysis of copies, notes that comparison is one of the most important tools used in the analysis of copies. Learning by comparing copies is possible only on the basis of comparison. This comparison process is not random, but rather it is purposeful to bring out their similarities and differences. The comparison is not simply between positive and negative copies;

B. Hasanli, in the textbook "Methodology of teaching literature", talks extensively about the analysis of literary works in literature classes, the consideration of genre features in the analysis of literary works, giving examples from literary works. B. Hasanli divides the principles of school analysis of artistic works into 5 parts. These principles can be explained sequentially as follows:

1. The principle of idealism. An idea is a set of concepts that reflect reality in the human mind and an attitude that forms the basis of a person's view of the world. In fiction, the idea plays the role of the idea, essence, which determines the content of the work. It should not be forgotten that each work has its own idea. Theme and idea are closely related. The creator of the work chooses that topic and idea based on the social relations, geographical, political conditions or, in the simplest way, the events he witnessed and the feelings he experienced. The work can be about love, friendship, family, war, loneliness and other topics. In general, to properly analyze the work, it is necessary to understand the spirit of the work. The idea is the soul of the work. Considering the principle of idealism, we can understand the author's thoughts and intentions.

2. The principle of historicity. The written works reflect many social-historical and literary features of their time. Therefore, we should analyze the work we are reading, taking into account the characteristics of the period in which it was written. For example, when analyzing any work of the famous Azerbaijani poet Imadedin Nasimi, who lived in the 14th century, it is necessary to take into account the period in which he lived and the date when the work was written. This is based on the principle of historicity. If we analyze Nasimi's ghazal "Sigmazam", we have to look at the period in which the poet lived and his life path. At this time, we will see that the idea of Hurufism was widespread at that time, that Nasimi promoted the idea of Hurufism, and that philosophical-pantheistic thoughts were expressed in the ghazal.

3. The principle of unity of content and form. Content and form are interrelated. Because content is expressed through form. When the author creates a work of art, he thinks about the form corresponding to

the content. For example, in the poem "Swallow" by Aliaga Kurchayli, he turned to the lyrical genre to express the fact that the swallow spreads its wings and flies despite the lightning and the rain, and takes food to its young in its beak. As it can be seen, the topic chosen by Aliaga Kurchayli has manifested itself in a certain form. For this reason, when analyzing a work of art, its content and form should be analyzed in a related manner.

4. Pedagogical principle. The teaching process is built taking into account the age, cognitive level, interest and needs of the students. For this reason, the pedagogical principle is of great importance in the analysis of the work. The language, volume, content and idea of the analyzed work should correspond to the student's age, interests and needs, and level of understanding. While mastering a work of art to students, at the same time, the skills of analyzing that work should be developed.

5. The principle of reconciliation of analysis ways and methods. The way of analysis is chosen according to the genre, volume and other characteristics of the work. The ways of analysis include analysis by the author, analysis by images, analysis by problem theme, analysis of the composition of the work, comparative analysis, etc. can be shown. The first three of these methods of analysis are taken as the basis in the methodology of teaching literature. The methods of analysis of the work should also be suitable for the work, the way of analysis of the work.

B. Hasanli writes the following about the analysis after the author: "The basis of the analysis after the author is the subject line, main event, and episode of the work. At this time, the analysis seems to repeat the process of reading the work in a more complex form. Thus, by focusing on the main episodes, behavioral motives of the hero, descriptions of nature, author's comments, it is ensured that the work is understood in the unity of content and form. [24, 191]"

Image analysis is also widely used when analyzing a work of art. The main idea in a work of art is conveyed through images. The author summarizes a certain group of human characteristics in the face of the characters he chooses. Each character has its own characteristics. During the analysis of these images, their characteristic aspects are revealed, and at the same time, the idea-content of the work, the idea that the author wants to convey to us is determined.

Problem analysis plays a great role in the correct understanding of the artistic work, in the creation of students' independent thoughts and approaches to the problems raised in the work. During problematic analysis, the analysis of a work of art begins with the discussion of the main problem in the work. For this, students are asked thought-provoking questions about the work at the beginning of the lesson. As a result, the resulting discussion encourages students to express their opinions.

S. Huseinoglu, in chapter I of the methodological manual "Literature teaching at school" under the heading "The principle of comparison and its use in the analysis of artistic works", "The use of the principle of comparison in the development of activity and

independence of students in literature lessons", "The independent work of students in the process of comparative teaching of artistic works" He talked extensively about the principle of comparison.

S. Huseinoglu writes that the principle of comparison is used in all parts of the training process. This includes: interpretation of new material, consolidation of the acquired information in memory, repetition of previous materials, etc.

Since all the elements of artistic works are connected to each other, in order to fully understand the work, to fully understand its idea, those elements must be clarified separately. For example, the images in the work are formed through language, composition, or the idea of the work is expressed through images. Apparently, there is a reciprocal relationship here. It is impossible to clarify the relationship between these elements without using the principle of comparison. For this reason, this principle is of special importance in the study of literature.

F. Yusifov is one of the methodists who talks about the issue of analysis of literary works in the school, the structure of analysis lessons, work on the analysis of the work. In his textbook "Methodology of teaching literature", F. Yusifov mentioned that the most important stage in the study of literary works is its analysis, that at this stage all the tasks set before the analysis are realized and many similar issues.

A. Hajiyeu mentioned the ways of artistic analysis of literary works in his book "Methods of Literary Works Analysis" and also in the textbook for higher school called "Methodology of Teaching Azerbaijani Literature", he talked about the ideological analysis and analysis of literary works according to their structure. He commented on the issues that should be paid attention to in the analysis of lyrical and dramatic works based on examples.

As it can be seen, since the last century, scientists and researchers have conducted research on the analysis of artistic works, the use of convenient methods during the analysis, and the positive aspects of using the comparison method, and the general result of all these studies have been reflected in the scientific-methodical literature.

Conclusion

It was investigated that literary works are given a special place in literature classes and that the process of teaching artistic works is one of the most important issues. The importance of studying the content of artistic works in the formation of students as a perfect person was clarified. Valuable scientists and Methodists' opinions on this matter were discussed.

The process of teaching the content of artistic works has always been investigated by our methodists and methods suitable for each century have been put forward. In this research work, the problems and solutions faced by classical methodists Aliyar Karabagli, Bilal Muradov, Jamal Ahmadov in the process of teaching the content of the works, the best methods and methods of learning are shown. In modern times, the process of teaching works has started to be taught in schools in the interactive teaching method. Soltan Huseynoglu, Bilal Hasanli, Fakhreddin Yusifov,

who are among the prominent methodists of the modern era, have been investigated and shown in the research work.

The interest of Eastern nations in literature and the similarities of their literature among nations were investigated. The educational system and the form of teaching literature in developed countries such as Germany, Russia, and Turkey and the methods used in the process of teaching the content of artistic works in those countries were explained. The teaching of literature in schools in Germany and the methods of teaching works were discussed.

The situation in secondary schools related to the problem was investigated and studied. In literature classes, the place of artistic works was clarified and the importance of vocabulary work, planning, and storytelling methods were discussed.

We would suggest that while teaching the content of the work, we should set up the right motivation for the students, express our opinions about the content of the work in advance, and create interest in the work in them. At the end of each work, write a dictionary of incomprehensible words.

Fiction is needed by students of all age levels. Regardless of grade level, every student should read fiction. They should discuss the works among themselves, inform and recommend each other. This kind of reading develops students' speech and artistic thinking. Therefore, we teachers should encourage our students to read fiction and enrich their literature. During vacations, we should instruct them to read literary works, introduce them to libraries, and in various ways make them a habit of reading literary works and make them love it.

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